

1 **Stage-specific transcription in platelets.**

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6 Platelets serve innate immune functions in humans by responding to injury or puncture and initiating
7 wound healing through clotting. We studied whole transcription in platelets differentiated *in vitro* from
8 human embryonic stem cells (hES) and in platelets (megakaryocytes) differentiated from hematopoietic
9 stem cells (HSCs). We observed at the transcriptional level the transition from embryonic stem cell, to
10 multipotent hematopoietic progenitor, to megakaryocyte, marked by induction of CD34, progression to an
11 MK/E progenitor, then differentiation to platelet. Platelets were marked by expression of CD55 and
12 TMEM40. We discovered and describe a group of Fc receptors whose expression was activated in the
13 platelet. Platelet-specific mRNAs included PTAFR, P-selectin, PF4, and heparanase. Transcriptome level
14 study of platelets using embryonic and hematopoietic stem cell culture systems *in vitro* enables
15 unprecedented transcriptional description of the megakaryocyte and megakaryocyte progenitors.
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